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Editorial

WE ARE EASTER PEOPLE

“We are Easter People and Alleluia is our song,” says St. Augustine. He says further that “every Christian must be a great Alleluia from head to toe.” The early Christians could not hold their joy and enthusiasm within themselves. They went around proclaiming, “Alleluia! He is Risen! And we have experienced his resurrection in our lives.” When we look at ourselves, do we find ourselves beaming with the joy of the Risen Lord? Like the early Christians, are we filled with the great excitement to share the good news with the world? We need to ask ourselves, “Have we experienced the resurrection in our lives?”

1. THE WAY OF EASTER: FROM THE DESERT TO THE PROMISED LAND

Pope Benedict XVI in his famous book *Jesus of Nazareth* quotes an anecdote on “Our Father prayer” from the book of Peter-Hans Kolvenbach, the former Superior General of the Society of Jesus, titled *Der österliche Weg (The Path to Easter)*. Pope Benedict writes:

Father Peter-Hans Kolvenbach... tells the story of a *staretz*, a spiritual advisor of the Eastern Church, who yearned to “begin the Our Father with the last verse, so that one might

become worthy to finish the prayer with the initial words—“Our Father.”” In this way, the *staretz* explained, we would be following the path to Easter. “We begin the desert with the temptation, we return to Egypt, then we travel the path of Exodus, through the stations of forgiveness and God’s manna, and by God’s will we attain the promised land, the kingdom of God, where he communicates us the mystery of his name: ‘Our Father’” (Der österliche Weg, pp. 65f.) [Pope Benedict XVI, *Jesus of Nazareth I* (Bloomsbury 2007), 135].

Forty days of Lenten journey through the wilderness helps us to reach the Promised Land, the Kingdom of God, where God is enthroned and honoured as the Father of all humanity. As the Lord’s Prayer in the reverse order suggests, not only the season of Lent but also our entire life is the way leading us to Easter.

2. THE ATTITUDE OF EASTER: FROM HOPELESSNESS TO HOPE-FILLED LIFE

Easter is not only a feast; it is an attitude. It is the attitude to move from our bent, bowed, and burdened existence to the hopeful and joyful life in Christ. This attitude helps us to believe that for us everything turns out for good. No matter how painful the situation is, there is always hope for us. This hope is founded in the Risen Lord. Because of this hope, our hearts become so emboldened that they do not fear anything, not even death. The sorrows and problems in life lose their poignancy and in turn become valuable stepping-stones in our life’s journey towards wholeness.

Death, darkness and negativity are part of human experience. Several times, we experience negative emotions engulfing us; darkness surrounding us; the forces of death taking hold of us. In the midst of these pervasively destructive forces, we feel beaten, burdened, and bowed down. In such situations, we cry out to the Lord, saying, “O God, O God, see how big are our problems!” However, after receiving the hope-filled Easter attitude, we can look at the same problems squarely, in a matter-of-fact way, and we can say boldly, “O

Problems, O Problems, see how big is our God. We are no longer afraid of you because Jesus has won victory for us. We are no longer afraid. We are free.”

3. THE MESSAGE OF EASTER: STONE ROLLED AWAY AND GOD RAISES US UP

The Resurrection narratives in the Gospels speak about the stone rolled away from the tomb (cf. Jn 20:1; Mt 28:2; Mk 16:4; Lk 24:2). Only Matthew mentions that an angel of the Lord rolled back the stone (Mt 28:2). John, Mark, and Luke employ the technique of “Divine Passive,” where the actor is not explicitly mentioned, but understood to be God. Luke uses God as the subject of “raising up” several times in the Acts (2:24.32; 3:15; 4:10; 5:30; 10:40; 13:30.37). Resurrection is the most supreme act of God. Resurrection brings God’s act of creation to its culmination. God removed the stone from the tomb of Jesus. God wishes to do the same for us too. God makes sure that several stones, barriers, hindrances, and burdens are removed from our paths and from our hearts, and our lives are made lighter, better, freer, and more meaningful.

Easter celebrates the total transformation of the deadly mess into the most life-giving message of resurrection. The message is loud and clear: The stone is rolled away by the power of God and God raises us up. God raises us up from our spiritual death, from our lethargy, from our addictions, from our indifference, from our lowly existence. He raises us up to the dignity and honour of being God’s children, being his prophets, his agents of mercy, and his channels of peace and reconciliation.

4. THE PEACE OF EASTER: FROM CONFLICT TO HARMONY

“*La pace sia con tutti voi*” (the peace be with you all). These were the first words of Pope Leo XIV from the Central Loggia of St. Peter’s Basilica. Peace was the first greeting of the Risen Lord, and in the Easter season last year, the newly elected Pontiff also offered to the war-torn troubled world

a message of peace. He did not limit this peace only to the Christian faithful, but to all the people all over the world.

The world is in need of peace. The world does not need peace, which is achieved through clever manipulation and through arm-twisting tactics. The world needs *Shalom*, the peace of the Lord, which is the peace rooted in love stronger than death, and which is extended even to the enemies. The Easter peace overcomes all troubles, all conflicts, and achieves perfect reconciliation and harmony.

5. THE MIRACLE OF EASTER: FROM COWARDICE TO COURAGE

Through his resurrection, Lord Jesus touched death and darkness and transformed them into life and light. The miraculous touch of the Risen Lord turned Galilean fishermen into bold and fearless preachers of the Gospel. They spread the Gospel to different corners of the world. In and through Easter, God touches humans and fills them with his Holy Spirit. When this happens, ordinary people become extraordinary, cowards become courageous, and the unlettered become wise.

In the Acts of the Apostles, we see Peter and John being brought before the Sanhedrin, the highest Jewish religious and political authority of their time. The contrast between the apostles and the members of Sanhedrin was striking. The members of Sanhedrin were rich, powerful, well-educated, and highly respected. On the other hand, the apostles were poor, powerless, uneducated, and contemptible. In spite of that, the courage and wisdom shown by them became legendary. After experiencing the power of Jesus' resurrection, the apostles became bold and fearless evangelizers. God wishes to bring such boldness and fearlessness in our lives too.

6. THE LITURGY OF EASTER: FROM DEATH TO LIFE

Easter Vigil Liturgy is the summit of all the liturgies. No liturgical celebration is as rich and meaningful as the solemn liturgical celebration of this most important feast of Christianity. The singing of the "Exsultet" (Easter Proclamation or

Exultation), praising the paschal candle as the light of Christ, reviews for Christian's salvation history culminating in Christ. The procession in darkness evokes the Exodus experience. On ordinary Sundays and other solemn feast days (including Christmas) we have altogether three readings (including the Gospel). However, on Easter we have nine readings, although in many Churches only five of them are read.

After forty days of Lent, finally the Church Choirs sing the great Alleluia, ushering in the joy and peace of Christ, the newness and rejuvenation within us. During the Easter Vigil, catechumens receive baptism and all the faithful renew their baptismal promises. The faithful reject sin and profess to die to sin; they accept a new life in Jesus and commit themselves to live for Jesus. St. Paul beautifully combines the sacrament of baptism with Jesus' death and resurrection. In baptism, we die to our older, sinful self and we come out as a new creation. In the older ritual of baptism, one would get totally submerged in water signifying death and burial; the coming out of water represented new life in Christ.

7. THE PSALM OF EASTER: I SHALL NOT DIE, I SHALL LIVE

Ps 118 is the psalm often used in the Easter times. It is the last of the Egyptian Hallel (praise) psalms sung during the Passover festival of Jews (Pss 113-118). This psalm was the favourite psalm of Martin Luther. Ps 118:17 gives us a renewed hope by stating: "I shall not die, but I shall live, and recount the deeds of the Lord." Martin Luther wrote about this psalm: "the dying live; the suffering rejoice; the fallen rise; the disgraced are honoured." This psalm is filled with optimism and hope.

I shall not die; I shall not be suppressed; I shall not be discouraged; I shall not be frustrated. I shall live; I shall be filled with optimism; I shall be brimming with joy and hope. This is the statement of Easter; this is the sentiment of everyone who believes in the feast of resurrection. Easter gives the message of undying hope, of indomitable optimism.

Who can destroy our joy? Who can take away hope from our hearts? No one! Nothing! We are made unconquerable; Christ Jesus has made us invincible.

CONCLUSION

Easter is that special season where we move from our bent, bowed, and burdened existence to a 'risen' and hope-filled life. It is a time for the dry plant of our life to bear tender shoots; it is a period for us to play the sweetest melody we have never played before. It is the season to realize that in the bosom of death, there is a tiny sprout of resurrection. It is the *kairos* to believe that all shall be well and all manner of things shall be well. No matter how desperate the situation, there is always hope for us because of Jesus' resurrection.

God has given us this life to live it filled with hope and joy. Resurrection invites us to enjoy every step that we take on life's journey. As Christians, we are not called to drag our feet on the path of life, but to take bold and courageous steps to usher a new age. This Easter my prayer for all of us is: May we always have a smile on our lips, a spark in our eyes, music in our ears, love and hope in our hearts, and a spring in our steps, ready to dance at the music of the Master. Wishing you all a hope-filled life in the Risen Lord Jesus Christ.

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The Editorial Board of

Vidyajyoti Journal of Theological Reflection

wishes the Readers and Well-wishers

a Hope-filled and Blessed Easter!

May the Peace of the Risen Lord

rule over our Hearts!